

Left Handed Coordinate System for Antimatter Implies that Antiphotons are Distinct from Photons

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Abstract

According to the current interpretations of the standard model, photons are their own antiparticles [?]. However, if we slightly modify our view of antimatter, we see that photons and antiphotons could be different particles. Even though photons and antiphotons have the same charge, their electro-magnetic waves might not be the same. A right handed coordinate system for photons and a left handed coordinate system for antiphotons reveals their difference. There are also other effects including: 1) If photons and antiphotons do not annihilate each other, interference between them could result in waves of pure electric or magnetic energy. 2) Viewing matter and antimatter from a fourth dimension they are the same particles just rotated by π radians.

Introduction

We discuss the implications if antimatter is physically a left handed coordinate system for electric field, magnetic field and movement instead of a right handed coordinate system for normal matter. In other words, antimatter would not have an opposite charge as corresponding matter, rather it would have the same charge in the opposite direction. We explore four consequence for this hypothesis about antimatter. First we investigate the existence of antiphotons that are distinct from photons. Next we cover photons and antiphotons moving backwards in time. After that we explain why distinct antiphotons have not yet been recognized / detected. Finally we discuss the view of matter and antimatter from a fourth dimension.

Since handedness for the fundamental particles already describes their chirality or helicity, to avoid confusion due to duplicating terms we define Positive Coordinate System (PCS) for right handed Cartesian coordinate systems and Negative Coordinate System (NCS) for left handed Cartesian coordinate systems.

Theory

We hypothesize that the electric field, magnetic field, and direction of motion for normal matter is naturally PCS and antimatter is naturally NCS. If this is correct, the electric field for matter is in the opposite direction compared to matter. This implies that the photon and antiphoton are two distinct particles. To explore this possibility, we first review positive and negative coordinate systems. Then we investigate the implications of a PCS for normal matter and an NCS for antimatter.

Review of PCS vs NCS

If the thumb, pointing finger and middle finger of one hand are all at right angles and they respectively represent positive x, y and z, then the right hand identifies a PCS, while the left hand represents an NCS[?]. The diagram below depicts a PCS and an NCS.

Figure 1: PCS and NCS

PCS Photons and NCS Antiphotons

If we let the electric field be x, the magnetic field be y and the direction of motion be z, we can compare the electro-magnetic waves of PCS photons to NCS antiphotons.

Figure 2: Electro-magnetic Waves of Photon and Antiphoton

Since the diagram clearly shows that the electric field of the NCS antiphoton is in the opposite direction of the electric field of the PCS photon, we propose that NCS antiphotons and PCS photons are different particles.

Discussion

Backward in Time

Since antimatter particles look like their corresponding normal particles with opposite temporal direction[?], a PCS photon going backwards in time should appear the same as an NCS antiphoton moving forwards in time. Below is a diagram of a PCS photon moving backwards in time into the screen / paper and an NCS antiphoton moving forwards in time out of the screen / paper.

Figure 3: Photon Moving Backwards in Time and Antiphoton

Figure 3 clearly shows that a PCS photon moving backwards in time looks the same as an NCS antiphoton moving forward in time.

Photon / Antiphoton Annihilation or Interference

Since PCS photons and NCS antiphotons have zero charge they may not annihilate each other as in other matter and antimatter interactions. They may interfere with each other instead. When a PCS photon and an NCS antiphoton with the same frequency are synchronized such that the destructive interference cancels out their magnetic fields, the constructive interference results in a wave of electric energy. If one of the waves is shifted half a wavelength, the electric fields cancel resulting in a wave of magnetic energy.

Figure 4: Pure Electric and Magnetic Waves

The interference between the electro-magnetic waves of the PCS photon and NCS antiphoton can produce waves of pure electric or magnetic energy as displayed in Figure 4.

Why antiphotons have not been Recognized or Detected

NCS antiphotons actually have been detected in particle accelerators but not recognized as such. They are just masquerading as PCS photons. Since the frequency for photons and their corresponding

antiphotons are the same, detectors that rely on energy to detect photons perceive NCS antiphotons as PCS photons.

Although normal matter molecules emit PCS photons, antimatter molecules emit NCS antiphotons. Due to the difficulty in creating antimatter molecules, they may not have been thoroughly tested to determine if their emissions are PCS photons or NCS antiphotons.

View of Matter and Antimatter from a Fourth Dimension

If all the characteristics of antimatter are the same as the corresponding normal matter (other than the coordinate system), a particle of PCS matter / NCS antimatter rotated through a fourth dimension π radians around the magnetic field / movement plane results respectively in the corresponding particle of NCS antimatter / PCS matter. Starting with the formula for rotating a point in four dimensions around a plane, the equations below prove this transformation.

$$\begin{bmatrix} E' \\ B' \\ m' \\ w \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\Theta) & 0 & 0 & -\sin(\Theta) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \sin(\Theta) & 0 & 0 & \cos(\Theta) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} E \\ B \\ m \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad [?]$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} E' \\ B' \\ m' \\ w \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\Pi) & 0 & 0 & -\sin(\Pi) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \sin(\Pi) & 0 & 0 & \cos(\Pi) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} E \\ B \\ m \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} E' \\ B' \\ m' \\ w \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} E \\ B \\ m \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} E' \\ B' \\ m' \\ w \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -E \\ B \\ m \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Although the electric field is seems to be negated, we have shown that this can be interpreted as switching from a PCS to an NCS (or vice versa) – i.e., E has the same sign in the opposite direction.

Conclusion

It is possible that matter and antimatter have different coordinate systems resulting in antimatter having the same charge as matter but in the opposite direction. Experiments are should be conducted to test this hypothesis. If this conjecture is verified, it will enhance our understanding of antimatter and possibly enable new matter / antimatter interactions.

References

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